

Stability analysis of WAAM steel CHS columns with consideration of anisotropic behaviour

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ABSTRACT

Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM) steel opens up new opportunities in infrastructure construction. Circular hollow section (CHS) steel column components are most common in steel bridges and buildings. The paper presents buckling investigations on CHS columns fabricated by WAAM. Two building angles and imperfection geometries are considered in the buckling numeric models. The anisotropic behaviour of WAAM is considered by as-built material. Parametric analyses are carried out by the variation of the ratio between diameter and wall thickness. The applicability of second generation of Eurocode 3 is discussed regarding the provisions of stability. This study could contribute to the design theory of thin-walled WAAM steel members.

Keywords: WAAM, buckling, circular hollow section, 3D printing, anisotropic behaviour

1 INTRODUCTION

Additive Manufacturing (AM) has many potential benefits, such as reduced material consumption, and the ability to readily produce sophisticated structural component (1). Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM) is a type of AM that is highly efficient and cost-effective. It is particularly well-suited for the efficient, rapid and economical processing of large-sized complex parts. According to recent reports (2), WAAM is regarded as one of the most suitable metal additive manufacturing technologies for steel construction.

Although WAAM has great potentials, it still faces several technical challenges. These challenges include the concentration of heat in the wire during processing, the sensitive size of the melt pool, the large heat-affected zone and the low molding accuracy and surface quality of the samples (3,4). Several studies have investigated the anisotropy of WAAM stainless materials and the influence of inherent geometrical properties on mechanical properties (5,6,7,8). It is reported that the loading capacity of Circular Hollow Section (CHS) made from WAAM stainless steel materials is affected by the angle of construction (9). Among various relative deposition angles, the direction of vertical deposition had the smallest elastic modulus and yield strength. The behaviour of the cross-section of WAAM CHS steel columns was found to be similar to that of traditionally produced stainless steel CHS columns, and a slenderer cross-section was found to be more susceptible to the influence of local buckling (10). The rough surface of the WAAM CHS steel columns should also be considered (11,12). Silva et al (13) suggested that WAAM ‘mortise-and-tenon’ joints and demonstrated to have substantial potential to create joints between similar and dissimilar materials. In July 2021, the world's first 3D-printed metal bridge manufactured by a collaboration of MX3D, Arup Engineers and Imperial College was erected in the Netherlands (14). Gardner et al (15) conducted a series of test on the bridge construction, which include tensile tests on the material properties of the bridge, short-column tests on the critical parts of the bridge to assess the

mechanical properties of its members, full-scale structural load tests and finite element simulations under different operating conditions. Voelkel et al (16) conducted a fatigue study regarding the hot-dip galvanized additively manufactured steel. This paper aims to investigate the effects of three major factors - the relative deposition direction, wall thickness t , and cross-section diameter D - on the buckling behaviour of CHS steel columns.

2 MATERIAL PROPERTIES

The WAAM high-strength low-alloy steel material of CHS column has been adopted from reference (17). Coupons have been extracted at 0° (horizontal), 45° (diagonal), and 90° (vertical) relative to the deposition direction, as shown in *Fig.1*. The anisotropic and geometric properties of WAAM-forming material were investigated for their effect on CHS steel columns. The process parameters are summarized in *Table 1*.

Table 1. Process parameters of the WAAM steel (17)

Process parameters	Value
Feedstock wire	AM80HD
Wire diameter	1.2mm
Welding current	75A
Welding voltage	13.1V
Wire feed speed	2m/min
Torch travel speed	25cm/min

Fig.1. Orientation of tensile coupons extracted from the WAAM-HSLA plate

A summary of the average material properties is reported in *Table 2*, including the direction of testing relative to the deposition direction θ , Young's modulus E , 0.2% proof stress $\sigma_{0.2}$, tensile strength f_y , poisson's ratio ν and hardening index n . The results show that the material exhibits θ -dependent anisotropy.

Table 2. Material properties

θ	E [GPa]	$\sigma_{0.2}$ [MPa]	f_y [MPa]	ν	n
0°	200.89	728	887	0.295	36.243
45°	202.10	765	898	0.290	42.145
90°	200.08	726	890	0.287	45.281

With regard to the roughness of WAAM steel, the authors have suggested a surface roughness model (17), which is used here. The model is defined as Eq. (1). The specific parameters are shown in *Table 3*. The stress-strain curves are derived from the model as plotted in *Fig.2*.

$$f(x) = (P_2 \sin(\pi \frac{x}{P_1}) + p_3) - p_2 \quad (1)$$

Table 3. Rounded properties of the measured surfaces for statistical description of the surface profiles

Parameters	Average [mm]	Standard deviation[mm]
P ₁	2.6	0.1
P ₂	0.25	0.05
P ₃	0	0.05

The WAAM surface roughness model proposed by Feldmann et al. was used to obtain a more realistic stress-strain curve as shown in *fig.2*.

Fig.2. Stress-strain curves for specimens with different orientations.

3 NUMERICAL STUDY

In this section, a numerical model of the WAAM stainless steel CHS steel column was first established using Gardner's WAAM CHS steel columns tests (10) to verify its accuracy. Then, a parametric study of the local buckling resistance of the CHS steel columns was conducted, in which the local slenderness of section range ($D/t\epsilon^2 = 40.54\sim 268.9$) and the material's three deposition directions were accounted for a wider range of geometric shapes.

3.1 Modelling details

The thickness of the CHS steel columns unit was far less than its structural dimensions, thus, surface reduction integration shells (S4R) were employed for FE analysis. Quadrilateral sweep meshing was used for modelling. Based on previous FE analysis studies on stainless steel CHS steel columns, it was found that a 1x1 mm mesh size could accurately capture the local buckling failure mode of the CHS steel columns.

With regard to the boundary conditions, all degrees of freedom on one end of the column were constrained, and on the other end of column axial displacement was applied as shown in *Fig.3*.

Fig.3. Finite Element Model Constraint Setting

Initial geometric defects were introduced into the FE model to evaluate the local buckling performance of the WAAM CHS steel columns. According to Zhang et al. (10), the localized defect magnitude was defined as $0.01(D/t)^{1/2}$.

The numeric calculations were carried out in two steps. Firstly, the linear elastic buckling loads and modes were found by the buckle analysis step in ABAQUS. The second step of the elasto-plastic analysis was performed by using the arc length approach, taking the load amplitude as an unknown while solving for the load displacements.

3.2 Numeric model validation

Numeric models have been established to validate the accuracy against the test data (10). The ultimate loads of FE models are compared with the corresponding test results in *Table.4*. The average of $N_{u,FE} / N_{u,test}$ results to 1.04. Differences between test results complying with conventional stainless steel tube load carrying capacity and FE results are roughly within 5%.

Table.4 Comparison of ultimate loads between test and numerical results

Specimen	D [mm]	t [mm]	L [mm]	$N_{u,FE}$ [kN]	$N_{u,test}$ [kN]*	$N_{u,test}/N_{u,FE}$
FE1	74.97	1.07	207.74	107.5	106.4	0.989
FE2	74.97	2.09	207.65	228.1	229.0	1.004
FE3	7.97	3.10	207.65	350.0	356.3	1.018
FE4	75.01	4.06	207.42	459.6	498.0	1.083
FE5	75.01	5.10	207.62	598.0	663.4	1.109
Average						1.04

*: According to Zhang (10)

3.3 Parametric studies

In order to obtain additional data to evaluate the existing design methods and give corresponding design suggestions, a series of parametric studies were carried out using the validated FE model. The dimensions of the FE models in the parametric study are presented in *Table 5*, where $D/t\epsilon^2$ is the local slenderness of section. Three different wall thicknesses t are chosen in the parametric study. The diameter D of the cross-section varied to cover a wide range of from Class 1 to Class 3 sections as defined by EN 1993-1-4 (19). The length L is selected as four times the diameter D to include a representative distribution of local imperfections and to exclude global buckling (20). The local buckling damage pattern is shown in *Fig.4* and *Fig.5*, and the results of parametric calculation are shown in *Fig.6*.

Fig.4. Local initial geometric defects

Fig.5. Local buckling failure pattern

Table 5 The dimensions of the FE models in the parametric study

t [mm]	D [mm]	L [mm]	$D/t\epsilon^2$
4	130,160,		
6	190,220,250,	4D	40.54~268.9
8	280,310		

$$\epsilon = (235E / (210000f_y))^{0.5}$$

$$(1)$$

Fig.6 Peak load comparison diagram

From Fig.6, it is found that the deposition direction θ has a significant effect on the $N_{u,FE}$ (ultimate bearing capacity) of the WAAM CHS steel columns. The column exhibits greater $N_{u,FE}$ in the 0° direction than in the 45° and 90° directions for different D and t . $N_{u,FE}$ is linearly correlated with the diameter D , and the slope is positively correlated with the wall thickness t . The $N_{u,FE}$ is also linearly correlated with the diameter D and positively correlated with the wall thickness t .

4 EVALUATION OF DESIGN METHODS FOR EN 1993

In this section, the applicability of EN 1993-1-4 (19) to WAAM CHS steel columns is evaluated by means of numerical results. EN 1993-1-4 is based on a member width/thickness ratio divided into three types of cross-sections, and the ultimate load carrying capacity of axial compression members is calculated according to the following equation:

$$D/t \leq \begin{cases} 50\varepsilon^2, & \text{class 1} \\ 70\varepsilon^2, & \text{class 2} \\ 280\varepsilon^2, & \text{class 3} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Class1-3:

$$N_{b,Rd} = \frac{\chi A \sigma_{0.2}}{\gamma_{M1}} \quad (3)$$

The ratio between the numerical result of the FE model and the values from EN 1993 $N_{u,FE}/N_{u,EN}$ is plotted in Fig.7, in which the wall thickness t has a significant influence. All the data are divided into 3 curves in Fig.7. In class 1, $N_{u,FE} \approx 1.5N_{u,EN}$ and EN 1993 is conservative; in class 2, EN 1993 is conservative at $t = 6$, but $N_{u,FE} < N_{u,EN}$ at $t = 8$. In particular, in class 3, the data are further dispersed, with all $N_{u,FE} < N_{u,EN}$ at $t = 8$; at $t = 6$, $D/t\varepsilon^2 \geq 118$ $N_{u,FE} < N_{u,EN}$; and in $t=4$, $N_{u,FE} < N_{u,EN}$ only for $D/t\varepsilon^2 \geq 250$.

Fig.7 Comparisons of compressive capacities of FE models with predictions by EN 1993-1-4

5 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The paper presents the local buckling research of WAAM CHS steel columns. Parametric numerical analysis is performed involving surface roughness and initial defects. The numeric value is compared with the EN 1993-1-4 value. The following conclusions can be drawn:

- A numerical model of WAAM CHS steel columns considering both anisotropic material properties and surface roughness is proposed to analyse the local slenderness.
- For the same wall thickness, the ultimate capacity of WAAM CHS column is linearly correlated with the diameter D and the slope is positively correlated with the wall thickness.
- According to the results, EN 1993-1-4 provision suit well for WAAM CHS steel columns with small wall thicknesses. There are good predictions for CHS steel columns with wall thicknesses less than 8 mm in class 1 and 2 sections, however, for wall thicknesses greater than 4 mm in class 3 sections, large deviation may occur.

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REFERENCES

1. Feldmann, M., Kühne, R., Citarelli, S., Reisgen, U., Sharma, R., & Oster, L. (2019). 3D-Drucken im Stahlbau mit dem automatisierten Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing. *Stahlbau*, 203–213. <https://doi.org/10.1002/stab.201800029>
2. Kühne, R., Feldmann, M., Citarelli, S., Reisgen, U., Sharma, R., & Oster, L. (2019). 3D printing in steel construction with the automated Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing. *Ce/Papers*, 577–583. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cepa.1103>
3. Bartsch, H., Kühne, R., Citarelli, S., Schaffrath, S., & Feldmann, M. (2021). Fatigue analysis of wire arc additive manufactured (3D printed) components with unmilled surface. *Structures*, 576–589. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.istruc.2021.01.068>
4. Dinovitzer, M., Chen, X., Laliberte, J., Huang, X., & Frei, H. (2019). Effect of wire and arc additive manufacturing (WAAM) process parameters on bead geometry and microstructure. *Additive Manufacturing*, 138–146. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2018.12.013>
5. Laghi, V., Palermo, M., Gasparini, G., Girelli, V. A., & Trombetti, T. (2021). On the influence of the geometrical irregularities in the mechanical response of Wire-and-Arc Additively Manufactured planar elements. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, 106490. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcsr.2020.106490>
6. Evans, S. I., Wang, J., Qin, J., He, Y., Shepherd, P., & Ding, J. (2022). A review of WAAM for steel construction – Manufacturing, material and geometric properties, design, and future directions. *Structures*, 1506–1522. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.istruc.2022.08.084>
7. Haden, C. V., Zeng, G., Carter, F. M., Ruhl, C., Krick, B. A., & Harlow, D. G. (2017). Wire and arc additive manufactured steel: Tensile and wear properties. *Additive Manufacturing*, 115–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2017.05.010>
8. Huang, C., Kyvelou, P., Zhang, R., Ben Britton, T., & Gardner, L. (2022). Mechanical Testing and Microstructural Analysis of Wire Arc Additively Manufactured Steels. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4004790>
9. Huang, C., Meng, X., Buchanan, C., & Gardner, L. (2022). Flexural Buckling of Wire Arc Additively Manufactured Tubular Columns. *Journal of Structural Engineering*. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(asce\)st.1943-541x.0003427](https://doi.org/10.1061/(asce)st.1943-541x.0003427)
10. Zhang, R., Gardner, L., Buchanan, C., Matilainen, V.-P., Piili, H., & Salminen, A. (2021). Testing and analysis of additively manufactured stainless steel CHS in compression. *Thin-Walled Structures*, 107270. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tws.2020.107270>

11. Laghi, V., Tonelli, L., Palermo, M., Bruggi, M., Sola, R., Ceschini, L., & Trombetti, T. (2021). Experimentally-validated orthotropic elastic model for Wire-and-Arc Additively Manufactured stainless steel. *Additive Manufacturing*, 101999. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2021.101999>
12. Rodrigues, T. A., Duarte, V., Miranda, R. M., Santos, T. G., & Oliveira, J. P. (2019). Current Status and Perspectives on Wire and Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM). *Materials*, 1121. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma12071121>
13. Silva, D. F., Bragança, I. M., Silva, C. M., Alves, L. M., & Martins, P. A. (2019). Joining by forming of additive manufactured ‘mortise-and-tenon’ joints. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part B: Journal of Engineering Manufacture*, 166–173. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0954405417720954>
14. Buchanan, C., & Gardner, L. (2019). Metal 3D printing in construction: A review of methods, research, applications, opportunities and challenges. *Engineering Structures*, 332–348. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2018.11.045>
15. Gardner, L., Kyvelou, P., Herbert, G., & Buchanan, C. (2020). Testing and initial verification of the world’s first metal 3D printed bridge. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, 106233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcsr.2020.106233>
16. Voelkel, J., Kühne, R., Bartsch, H., Feldmann, M., Oster, L., Sharma, R., Reisgen, U., & Pinger, T. (2023). Fatigue strength of hot-dip galvanized additively manufactured steel. *Structures (Oxford)*, 58, 105364. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.istruc.2023.105364>
17. Jahns, H., Unglaub, J., Müller, J., Hensel, J., & Thiele, K. (2023). Material Behavior of High-Strength Low-Alloy Steel (HSLA) WAAM Walls in Construction. *Metals*, 13(3), 589. <https://doi.org/10.3390/met13030589>
18. Buchanan, C., Real, E., & Gardner, L. (2018). Testing, simulation and design of cold-formed stainless steel CHS columns. *Thin-Walled Structures*, 297–312. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tws.2018.05.006>
19. CEN, E. (2006). 3, Design of Steel Structures-Part 1-4: General Rules-Supplementary Rules for Stainless Steels. EN1993-1-4, European Committee for Standardization, Brussels, Belgium.
20. Ziemian, Ronald D. (2010). Guide to Stability Design Criteria for Metal Structures. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470549087>